

Low-Power and High-Throughput LUT-based Accelerator Architecture for Distributed CNN Inference at the Edge

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Abstract—Enabling distributed CNN inference at network’s edge demands efficient solutions due to resource limitations and strict timing and energy constraints. LUT-based architectures, which aims at storing pre-computed neural network layers as LUTs, allow eliminating external memory and enabling fast, energy-efficient inference. Their use into an ecosystem for distributed CNN processing across multiple edge devices opens the door to novel applications in the field of future mobility and aerospace. In this paper, we present a flow using LUT-based accelerators for distributed CNN inference at edge.

Index Terms—Embedded Artificial Intelligence (AI), Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), FPGA, Hardware accelerator

I. INTRODUCTION

The recent innovations in Artificial Intelligence (AI), and more specifically Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), have opened the way to new applications and markets, reshaping our daily lives and industries alike. However, with the continuous raise of the demand for real-time processing, arises an important need to implement these algorithms directly at the edge of networks, closer to the sensors and end-users. Implementing CNNs at the edge constitutes a major challenge, as CNNs are computational and memory-hungry while edge computing platforms have resource limitations and often strong timing and energy constraints. Especially, a bottleneck in edge devices is attributed to external memory accesses (e.g. DDRRAM), which generate considerable delays and surge the energy consumption of the system [1]. To alleviate this, several approaches from the state-of-the-art propose to optimize and minimize the use of external memories [2], without, however, getting rid of them completely. Instead in the ElasticAI approach [3], the proposed flow stores pre-computed convolutions as Look-Up Tables (LUTs) in FPGA, which completely suppresses the need for external memory.

Simultaneously, the edge of networks is often constituted of numerous embedded platforms. A current trend of research focuses on distributing the data processing among available devices to accelerate CNNs’ inference [4]. In the fields of future mobility and aerospace, this could pave the way to novel applications combining multiple data sources (e.g. different road users such as cars, cyclists, pedestrians... or the use of multiple satellites to allow trilateration for accurate indoor user localization [5]). In this context, we propose a flow for efficient CNN inference at the edge, using and extending ElasticAI’s approach on FPGA within an ecosystem for distributed inference on multiple edge devices.

II. ECOSYSTEM FOR DISTRIBUTED INFERENCE

To support distributed inference of CNN-based applications, we propose a network ecosystem presented in Figure 1. In this figure, yellow circles correspond to edge devices used in a networking configurations. On the left, three main requirements for the ecosystem are specified: **A**, **B** and **C**. To support AI inference, the system is equipped with an On Board Computer (OBC) which role is to ensure high throughput and energy efficiency of the computation of multiple CNNs (**A**). On the left of the figure, a zoom on the OBC is provided. The OBC is constituted of a FPGA, for fast and energy efficient AI inference using accelerators (**A.1**), and a micro-processor system for the execution of Software (SW) (**A.2**). The architecture of Hardware (HW) accelerators is based on the ElasticAI methodology, further presented in Section III. Once compiled and implemented, this architecture type is dedicated to one specific CNN. Multiple instances are thus necessary to allow the execution of several CNNs. A hypervisor and scheduler are used to manage the access of SW to the different instances of HW accelerators. In order to support efficient distributed inference, the scheduler may leverage power management techniques such as clock/power gating, to reduce power consumption of unused HW accelerators, and dynamic partial reconfiguration.

The proposed ecosystem must allow collecting data and schedule/split AI computation among several systems, for user defined application powered by CNNs (**B**). In the figure, we provide the example of trilateration, a technique to approximate the location of a signal source, which can be enhanced to support accurate indoor source localization

Fig. 1. Proposed ecosystem for distributed CNN inference at the edge.

Fig. 2. On the left: synthesis flow for ElasticAI-based CNN HW accelerator. On the right: zoom on the implementation of a convolution layer.

using CNNs [5]. The system must also be able to locate and network with nearby systems (C). Frequent updates of the network map are necessary to adapt to the evolving position of nodes and re-establish the routing among each others, also potentially leveraging AI. The proposition and development of this ecosystem is shared among several DLR institutes. We, the authors of this paper, focus on proposing innovative LUT-based AI accelerators (A.1) and ensuring their compatibility with the scheduler and hypervisor. To this end, we intend to use and extend the ElasticAI framework [3].

III. LUT-BASED ACCELERATOR ARCHITECTURE

ElasticAI [3] is based on the utilization of FPGA’s local memory elements (LUTs and registers) to store CNN parameters, thus alleviating the use of external memory and leading to improvements in timing and power. On the left of Figure 2, the ElasticAI flow is presented. First, the input CNN is trained with binarization, i.e. its parameters are encoded as binary. This is an essential step to enable the synthesis of the CNN’s layers as LUTs. The training and binarization are done with Tensorflow. The trained CNN in ONNX file format is then compiled to VHDL using the ElasticAI modules. This process aims at describing pre-computed layers of the CNN as LUTs, as this is shown on the right of Figure 2. The generated VHDL code can then be synthesized using third party tools such as Xilinx Vivado and the resulting bitstream can be used to program FPGAs with the accelerator.

On the right of Figure 2, we provide a zoom on an implementation of a Conv-1D layer with streaming input of data varying over time using the ElasticAI methodology. New data arrival is pushed on top of older data using push registers. Input data may include several channels of information (as illustrated by A, B and C in this example). The data is fed to a first array of LUTs, which aims at characterizing the evolution of information channels over time. The outputs are then fed to a second array of LUTs, which models the results of the pre-computed convolutions. After this step, the first convolution layer is completed. The results are stored and updated using a similar push register mechanism, which allows modeling the evolution of convolution results over time. Max and average pooling are implemented using combinatorial logical circuits. The results are, again, stored in push registers to account for temporal evolution, and to be processed by the next layer. Dense layers are also pre-computed and implemented as LUTs.

This methodology was evaluated in [6], by implementing CNN-based electrocardiogram recognition on a Spartan S15 FPGA. The accelerator uses 40% of the available LUTs and none of the block RAM and DSP circuitry. The implemented accelerator was evaluated with a throughput of 10 million samples per second and an energy cost of 26.2 nJ per sample in a streaming processing configuration.

IV. CHALLENGES AND FUTURE WORK

In this paper, we present the context of our approach aimed at enabling low-power and high-throughput inference of CNNs on distributed edge devices with FPGAs, featuring LUT-based accelerator architectures synthesized using the ElasticAI framework [3]. Currently ElasticAI does not support 2-dimensional and more convolution layers, which are essential for the processing of more complex applications in the domains of future mobility and aerospace. Challenges regarding the place and route and utilization of the FPGA device may also arise when considering more complex applications, which may require tremendous amount of resources to be implemented as LUT-based accelerators. Another key aspect to be considered is that the novel accelerator architecture will be used in a distributed edge computing paradigm, and shall provide high performance and energy efficiency under such requirement. In future work we will focus on addressing these research challenges.

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